

Why and How Did The Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee Come into Existence?

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Abstract This research paper discusses the reasons for the establishment of the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, the events and its emergence as a means of smooth maintenance of religious centers.

Keywords Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, British Government, Singh Sabha Movement, Gurdwaras, Mahants, Gurdwara Reform Movement.

Introduction It was the custom of the British that in whichever country they hoisted the imperial flag, they would also establish centers for the propagation of Christianity there. Therefore, as soon as they occupied Punjab, they started establishing bases or missions for the propagation of Christianity in the central places of Punjab. In 1851 AD, there were only about one and a half Christians in Punjab, but in 1880 AD, their number increased to more than one and a half thousand. Apart from the direct preaching centers of Christianity, Christians also opened mission schools at various places to spread the word. In them and in government schools, the Christian religious book 'Anjeel' was taught to every student and the children were motivated to embrace Christianity by giving education, sermons and enticements.

Objective of study

1. To study the historical background and circumstances that led to the formation of the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee.
2. To examine the key events and struggle of the Gurdwara reform movement that played a pivotal role in the creation of SGPC.
3. To evaluate how SGPC manages Gurdwaras in a democratic way with the help of Sikh Community.

Review of Literature

1. Harjinder Singh Dilgir, How was the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee formed?, Amritsar, 2000 explains the background and main events that led to the formation of the SGPC. It clearly describes the role of the Gurdwara Reform Movement and shows how Sikhs organized themselves to take control of their shrines.
2. Shamsheer Singh Ashok, Fifty Years History of the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee (1926-1976), Amritsar, 1982 presents fifty years of SGPC's history, covering its growth, activities, and challenges from 1926 to 1976. It is useful for understanding the committee's achievements in religious, educational, and social fields during this period.
3. Harvinder Singh Khalsa, Gurdwara Parbandhak Reform Movement: A Bloody Tale of the Times, Amritsar, 2022 describes the struggles and sacrifices made during the Gurdwara Reform Movement. It highlights the violence, martyrdoms, and difficult situations faced by Sikhs while fighting for control of their shrines. The work is useful for understanding the painful side of the movement and the spirit of sacrifice behind the formation of the SGPC.
4. The book Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee Shri Amritsar- 100th Anniversary of Establishment: History, Works and Achievements (2020) tells about the beginning, history, and main works of the SGPC in looking after Gurdwaras, education, and social service.

Main Text **Establishment of the Singh Sabha Movement**

Many Sikh students started leaving their religion and adopting Christianity. In 1873 AD, 4 Sikh students of Mission School Amritsar - Atar Singh, Sadhu Singh, Santokh Singh and Aya Singh etc., were ready to become Christians. On knowing this, many Sikh leaders tried to convince these students and prevented them from adopting Christianity with great difficulty. This incident inspired the intelligent Sikhs that it was necessary to take measures to protect the sect from such destruction and attacks. Finally, this incident became the immediate reason for the beginning of the Singh Sabha Movement. On October 1, 1873 AD, S. A gathering of leading Sikhs was held under the presidency of Thakur Singh Sandhwalia, and it was decided to form a new organization. Thus, in 1873 AD, the first Singh Sabha was established in Amritsar. Its first president was S. Thakur Singh Sandhwalia and secretary Giani Gian Singh was elected. Its main objective was

the spread of education, under which Khalsa schools and colleges were opened at various places to impart religious education to Sikh students.

In the last decade of the 19th century, a large number of Singh Sabhas and Khalsa Diwans were established at different places. To bring unity among these different Singh Sabhas and Khalsa Diwans, a common Shiromani Diwan of the Panth, 'Chief Khalsa Diwan', was established in Amritsar on 30th October, 1902 AD. Bhai Arjan Singh Bagria and S. Sundar Singh Majithia were appointed as its President and Secretary, respectively. Its main objective was to eradicate illiteracy and to speed up the Sikh educational movement. An important achievement of the Chief Khalsa Diwan in the field of education is the establishment of the Sikh Educational Conference in 1908 AD. The nature of this educational institution is non-governmental, and this institution works under the patronage of the Chief Khalsa Diwan Amritsar. At the beginning of this conference, the number of Khalsa schools was only 8, which by 1947 AD, with enthusiastic and continuous efforts, reached 340.

Mahants' occupation of Gurdwaras

During the Sikh struggle in the 19th century, when the Sikhs were beset by a storm of troubles, the Sikhs had to leave their homes and live in forests and jungles, so the care of the Gurdwaras came into the hands of the Mahants. The holy Gurdwaras where the Gurus had established Gurbani and Sangat, became the property of greedy and characterless Mahants. In 1849 AD, the British occupied Punjab, and the Mahants, who were in control of the Gurdwaras, became free. They introduced Brahminical customs, caste, caste discrimination and untouchability into the Gurdwaras as they pleased.

Need for a committee to manage the Gurdwara Sahibs smoothly

In such circumstances, the Sikh leaders at that time felt the need to form a committee to run the management of the Gurdwara Sahibs according to the Guru-Maryada. The Sikh leaders met the Lieutenant Governor of Punjab, R.T. Egerton, for this work, and the Viceroy of India, Lord Ripon, also got information about this. The Lieutenant Governor of Punjab, R.T. Egerton, wrote a letter to the Viceroy, Lord Ripon and warned him:-

(I think that it would be politically dangerous to place the management of the Sikh Gurdwaras in the hands of a committee independent of government control, and I hope that you will be help get such orders issued, which will continue the successful management that has been going on for the last 30 years.)

The British Government never liked the idea of the management of the Gurdwaras going into the hands of the Sikhs. The Government wanted that adulteration in the Sikh religion should increase, the propagation of Sikhism should decrease, and the condition of the Gurdwaras should deteriorate. The Khalsa Diwan Lahore, in its session held from April 6 to April 8, 1907, demanded that the government-nominated Sarbraha of the Darbar Sahib be removed and the management of the Darbar Sahib should be placed under the control of a committee of Sikh chiefs. In 1912, J. Kartar Singh Jhabbar formed an organization called "Khalsa Diwan Khara Sauda Bar," and in 1914, Bhai Mehtab Singh Bir formed a "Biradari" group and started the work of Gurdwara reform. On January 14, 1914, the issue of Gurdwara Rakab Ganj Sahib started. After this, the Rowlatt Act was made by the British government and on April 13, 1919, the tragedy of Jallianwala Bagh took place. Gurdwaras, which are spiritual, scientific, communal, and national schools of the Sikhs, were implementing non-Sikh morality by the Mahants.

In such circumstances, the Sikhs felt the need for a new organization to run the management of the Gurdwaras according to the Gurdwara customs. As a result, the Sikh League (later the Central Sikh League) was established on December 27, 1919, but this Sikh League remained only a paper organization. On May 21, 1920, the Akali newspaper began to be published. This brought together the Sikh workers and Sikh leaders living far apart. In 1920, the Gurdwara Reform Movement began, under which the first front was Gurdwara Chumala Sahib (Patshahi VI), Lahore, which was successfully conquered on September 27, 1920, and on October 6, 1920, Gurdwara Baba Di Ber (Sialkot) also came under the control of the Sikhs.

After this, the priests of Akal Takht Sahib fled, fearing the Sikh congregation, leaving the Takht Sahib empty. The congregation formed a committee of 17 Singhs to take care of the service of Akal Takht Sahib. Jathedar Teja Singh Bhuchar was made the Jathedar of Akal Takht Sahib. On 13 October, the Deputy Commissioner called a meeting of priests, sarbarahs and Sikh leaders. Only Sikh leaders attended the meeting. On this, the DC formed a 9-member committee to take care of the service of Sri Darbar Sahib.

Sarbat Khalsa Assembly

During these days, Master Mota Singh came to Amritsar and advised to convene a Sarbat Khalsa Assembly of the Sikh Panth to elect a management committee to take over the management of the Gurdwara Sahib. On this, Dr. Gurbaksh Singh (who was a member of the 9-member committee) issued the "Hukmanama of Akal Takht Sahib" in the name of the Sikh community. At the end of this Hukmanama, Dr. Gurbaksh Singh signed as "Servant, Akal Takht Sahib".

The Hukamnama was as follows:-

"It is to be known to the entire Khalsa Ji that on 1 Maghar 1977, Sammat Nanakshahi 451, on 15 November 1920, at 9 a.m. a great Panthic gathering will be held in front of Akal Takht Sahib, in which, after deep deliberation, a representative Panthic Committee will be elected for the arrangements of Darbar Sahib Amritsar and all the Gurdwaras etc. Therefore, the following Singhs should be selected and sent to the Sarbat Guru Takhts, Gurdwaras, Khalsa Jathas, Sikh Battalions, State Sikh Forces, as per the following scheme:

Representative's qualification:

1. Must be Amritdhari, 2. Must be a regular of the five banis, 3. Must be a follower of the five kakars, 4. Must be one who gets up early in the morning (at night), 5. Must be one who pays the tenth.

Selection of Representatives Voting:

1. 5-5 from each Takht, 2. 1-1 from Gurdwaras, 3. 5 per 100 from Khalsa Jathas, 4. 6 from 6 Management Committees from Schools and Colleges, 8 from Teachers, 7 from Students, 5. 5 from Sikh States, 6. 2-2 from Sikh Magazines, 7. 2-2 from Sikh Platoons, 8. 5-5 if there is a complete Sikh Platoon, 9. 5 per 100 from Nihang Singh Jathas.

The decision of this committee will be announced in the entire Sikh Sangat, in which all devotees of the Guru Ghar can participate. So all lovers should please visit.

Note: The writing regarding this Diwan should be done with a learned servant. While this advertisement has been tried to reach the Guru Khalsa islands, etc., each participating representative should have a certificate from his Jathedar. "The Preacher, Dr. Gurbaksh Singh, Servant of Akal Takht Sahib, Amritsar."

Establishment of Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee

In the last week of October, a large number of Sikh leaders, Sikh professors, and students gathered at Khalsa College, Amritsar. Discussions were held on forming an organization for the maintenance of Gurdwaras. Some of the attendees wanted the Chief Khalsa to amend the constitution and hand over the management of Gurdwaras to him. This gathering passed a resolution presented by Bawa Harkishan Singh that talks should be held with the leaders of the Chief Khalsa Diwan so that a committee could be formed for the maintenance of Gurdwaras. In this regard, a 35-member committee was formed, and it was decided that this committee should meet the leaders of the Chief Khalsa Diwan and present a report in the Sarbat Khalsa gathering to be held on November 15. The 35-member committee met the leaders of the Chief Khalsa Diwan and held discussions with them, but no results were achieved. On 7th November, a meeting was held at Akal Takht Sahib for deliberations, and it was decided that the Sikhs had no other option but to elect a committee to look after the Gurdwaras in the Sarbat Khalsa meeting to be held on 15th November.

Two days before the Sarbat Khalsa meeting (15th November) (on 13th November), Maharaja Bhupindra Singh (Patiala), Sundar Singh Majitha, Bachittar Singh Patiala, Nihal Singh Patiala, Takht Singh Ferozepur, Sohan Singh Rawalpindi, Raghbir Singh Sandhawalia, Mihar Singh Lahore, Prof. Jodh Singh, Fateh Singh Granthi, Man Singh Ambala, Sundar Singh Ramgarhia, Shivdev Singh Sialkot met the Governor of Punjab. They all hatched a scheme to prevent the formation of the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee. The Governor of Punjab announced a 36-member committee for the management of the Gurdwaras, and Mr. Harbans Singh Attari was made the president of this committee.

Despite the formation of this 36-member committee, finally on November 15, 1920, a meeting of the Sarbat Khalsa was held, and in it the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, also known as the "PARLIAMENT OF SIKH NATION", was established. In this meeting, about 150 members of the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee were elected. Some of these members were also from the 36-member committee elected by the government. To prevent any conflict with the government, it was decided that the members of the government's (36-member) committee who were not elected should also be included in this committee. With this, the total number of members of the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee became 175. A meeting was held the next day to elect the president (Jathedar) of the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee. By 7 pm, the president of the Shiromani Committee was elected. The names of Harbans Singh Attari, Bhai Jodh Singh and Sundar Singh Majithia were proposed for the presidency. Most of the members present supported Sundar Singh Majithia. Finally, Sundar Singh Majithia was elected president, Harbans Singh Attari was elected vice-president, Sundar Singh Ramgarhia was elected secretary, and Baba Harkrishan Singh was elected vice-secretary. A few weeks later, Sundar Singh Majithia became a member of the executive council, and Harbans Singh Attari became the president in his place.

Establishment of Akali Dal (Political Party)

After the establishment of the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, the Sikhs felt the need for a political party to protect their Panthic interests, which could put pressure on the government to satisfy the demands of the Sikhs and implement the Panthic agenda of the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee. According to the 'Panch' newspaper, Master Mota Singh published an appeal in the newspaper and suggested the establishment of a 'Gurdwara Sevak Dal'. This appeal was as follows:-

Gurdwara Sevak Dal

Five hundred Singhs needed

A meeting was called at Akal Takht Sahib on 14th December for the establishment of this 'Gurdwara Sevak Dal' or 'Akali Dal'. Jathedar Kartar Singh Jhabbar proposed in this gathering: "Time is forcing us to urgently reform the Gurdwaras, and for this, everyone needs to make sacrifices. So, it should be done in such a way that the Akali Dal should be established. Its servants should devote at least one month in a year to the Panth. The center should be Amritsar, where 100 Singhs should be present at all times and as many Singhs as are needed should be sent wherever. Its branches should be formed in the areas."

Finally, 29 days after the establishment of the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, the 'Gurdwara Sewak Dal' was established on 14 December 1920 AD. On 23 January 1921 AD, a 2-day meeting was held at Akal Takht Sahib, in which everyone approved the name of this organization as 'Akali Dal' instead of 'Gurdwara Sewak Dal'. Sardar Sarmukh Singh Jhabal was elected the first Jathedar of this party. On 30 April 1921, the Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee was registered. On 14 August 1921, a new election of the 'Akali Dal' (Gurdwara Sevak Dal) was held, in which President Kharak Singh Ji Rais Sialkot, Vice-President S. Sundar Singh Ramgarhia, and Secretary S. Bahadur Mehtab Singh Ji Barrister were elected. On 29 March 1922, the Akali Dal, as per its sixth resolution, changed the name of the 'Akali Dal' organization to 'Shiromani Akali Dal'.

The Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee worked with great enthusiasm to improve the Gurdwara administration. The Mahants and priests were encouraged to hand over the Gurdwara Panth to the elected committee under them. Those who agreed were given salaries, houses to live in, etc., and the Sikh leaders had to make immense sacrifices to bring the Gurdwaras under the Panthic system from those who obstructed them. The Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee, the foremost religious organization of the Sikh Panth, and the Shiromani Akali Dal fought a long struggle from 1920 to 1925 during the Gurdwara Management Reform Movement, and set up numerous fronts. Bloody massacres took place, more than 2,000 Sikhs and Sikh women sacrificed their lives, more than 50,000 Sikhs who were loyal to the Panth suffered torture by the British government while serving jail terms, had their properties attached, and the Sikh community paid more than 16 lakh rupees as fines.

Conclusion

Finally, after historical fronts and unprecedented sacrifices, the Gurdwaras became independent. As a result, the bill was introduced in the Punjab Legislative Council on May 7, 1925. First, this bill was sent to a special committee for reading. On June 20, 1925, the committee gave its report, and on July 7, the bill was passed by the council. As soon as the Gurdwara Act was passed, the old Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee came to an end, and in its place, the management of the Gurdwaras was placed under the elected representatives of the newly formed committee "Central Board". On August 7, the bill was published in the Punjab Government Gazette. From November 1, 1925, the bill came into force as the Sikh Gurdwara Act 1925 (Punjab Act No. 8, 1925). The first meeting of the elected members of the 'Gurdwara Central Board' was held on September 4, 1926, at the Town Hall in Amritsar and 14 members were nominated in this meeting. Thus, the 'Gurdwara Central Board' was completed, and the meeting of the entire board was held again on 2nd October, 1926 AD in the Town Hall. In this meeting, the office bearers of the board and the internal committee were elected, and on the proposal of S. Amar Singh Ji, with the support of S. Harbans Singh, it was unanimously passed in this meeting that the name of this organization should be changed from Gurdwara Central Board to 'Shiromani Gurdwara Parbandhak Committee'. The government accepted this name. The first committee started giving charge to this newly formed committee on 26th November, 1926 AD and by 4th December, 1926 AD, it absorbed itself in it by giving full charge. Amendments were made to this Gurdwara Act from time to time as per the need, and it was kept abreast of contemporary problems.

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